

Maxwell Spin Cups, a mechanism for quantising electric potential.

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Abstract

This paper posits the existence of an electro-magnetic structure; the *Maxwell Spin Cup* that gives rise to what appears to be quantised charge. The *Maxwell Spin Cup* consists of two rotating magnetic potentials. The magnetic potentials themselves are displaced forwards and backwards in time from the current time plane. The rotating magnetic fields maintain a raised electric potential in the vicinity's of the pair. The paper postulates a time displacement force (a *time like force*) that draws the regions of forward displaced time and backwards displaced time together. The spin of the pair balances the centripetal *time like force*.

It is probable that a neutrino is just two empty regions of time displaced space rotating around each other. The paper sets out the model of the *Maxwell Spin Cup* and proposes a mechanism by which they can be created from high energy photons. There are 4 possible configurations of the simplest *Maxwell Spin Cup* and they correspond to: spin-up-electrons, spin-down-electron, spin-up-positrons, spin-down-positrons.

Keywords: *origin of spin 1/2 particles, origin of quantisation of charge in particles, neutrino spin 1/2 temporal shift*

1 Introduction

Electrons (and positrons) have a series of documented properties:

- quantised charge [6].
- spin of +/- 1/2 [2].
- magnetic dipole moment [8, 7].
- electric dipole moment [10]
- rest mass [4].

Prior to this paper no satisfactory explanation has been given for why particle charge is quantised, what exactly gives rise to a spin 1/2 particle or why an electron should have a magnetic dipole moment or indeed an electric dipole moment. No explanation exists of the process by which a high energy gamma ray photon creates an electron/positron pair at a scattering event or any plausible explanation of what a neutrino is or what it is for.

This paper proposes a stable electro-magnetic structure that we term a *Maxwell Spin Cup* that maintains a region of raised electric potential. It also proposes a mechanism by which such a structure can be created by temporal drag in a scattering event.

The creation process naturally gives rise to a pair of oppositely charged *Maxwell Spin Cups*. Consideration of the creation process and the mysterious nature of spin 1/2 particles leads to the conclusion that it is possible to displace regions of space time *in* time. The displacement in time of a pair of regions, one forwards and one backwards seems to create a force between the regions. A pair of temporally displaced regions rotating about each other will have intrinsic angular momentum, it is likely that if the regions are empty then you have a neutrino. We call a pair of temporally displaced rotating regions a *Sinclair Pair*.

This paper is laid out as follows, section 2 illiterates the structure of a *Maxwell Spin Cup* and shows the 4 different configurations that correspond to spin-up-electrons, spin-down-electrons, spin-up-positrons and spin-down-positrons. The differing magnetic quadruple moments of the spin-up and spin-down versions account for the existence of Cooper-pairs. Apparent quantisation of charge results from there being one stable set of values for angular momentum, temporal displacement and spatial displacement in the *Sinclair Pair*. Section 2.1 illustrates how a differential time like drag on a photon can distort it sufficiently to create a pair of *Maxwell Spin Cups*.

Future directions are considered and conclusions are given.

2 Maxwell Spin Cups

Figure 2 illustrates a Maxwell Spin Cup. The spin cup comprises two gobits of space time one displaced forwards in time and one displaced backwards in time (a Sinclair Pair), separated by some radial distance, each contains a magnetic potential. The gobits of space time rotate around an axis in space. The force that holds the two regions of space together is termed a time like force and is a bit like Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. It is beyond the scope of this paper to justify the existence of the time like force mathematically. This model gives rise to 4 distinct spin cups for the two possible senses of the magnetic fields and two directions of rotation. The magnitudes of the two magnetic potentials are assumed to be equal. It is beyond the scope of this paper to give a mathematical description of the distribution of potential created but it is very likely to have a dipole moment aligned with the spin axis and it is likely to be toroidal in nature.

There are four possible configurations for a simple Maxwell Spin Cup. The

Maxwell Spin Cup

Figure 1: A Maxwell Spin Cup with its Sinclair Pair. Rotating magnetic potentials hold the electrical potential in the vicinity of the cup away from zero. The two regions occupied by the magnetic potentials are displaced from each other in time and space. The fuchsia region is forward in time (displaced forward in time from the current time plane) and the blue region is displaced backwards in time.

magnetic field vectors [5] can be arranged [N-SS-N] or [S-NN-S] and the direction of rotation can be either clockwise or anti-clockwise. The four possible Maxwell Spin Cups are illustrated in figure 2.

The spin up-ness and spin down-ness are governed by the pairings of the magnetic field vectors, either [N-SS-N] or [S-NN-S]. It is obvious that there is the possibility for spin up and spin down electrons to attract each other through rotating quadruple alignment if they share a common spin axis. As one has spin $1/2$ and the other spin $-1/2$ the combined pair will have spin 0. This predicted behaviour corresponds to the creation of Cooper pairs [1].

2.1 Creation of Maxwell Spin Cups

Figure 2.1 shows the electric and magnetic fields of a photon plotted along a time or space axis.

As a photon passes a General Relativistic [3] space-time gradient the wave

The 4 simple Maxwell Spin Cups

Figure 2: The four simple Maxwell Spin Cups for electron-spin-up, electron-spin-down, positron-spin-up, positron-spin-down.

form is distorted. The distortion will become unstable if the fields become multi-valued for a given portion of the photon.

The energy required in a photon for it to be capable of creating an electron-positron pair is 1.022 MeV in broad terms this corresponds to a wavelength of $1.213 \times 10^{-12}m$. This is going to be an upper bound on order of magnitude of the separation of the two electric field fragments and the temporal separation of the field fragments is going to be of the order of $1/4$ of $(1/\text{frequency})$ or about 10^{-20} seconds. The volume in which charge is confined will be smaller than the rotating radius of the *Sinclair Pair*. The quoted classical radius of an electron seems to be $< 2.817910^{-15}m$. The numbers don't appear to be catastrophically different given the length of the arms being waved.

The conditions for a photon shedding a pair of Maxwell Spin Cups is likely to be very specific. The time dilation across the photon will likely have to align portions of the magnetic field that are the same length. The phase of the photon

Figure 3: Illustrative photon magnetic (blue) and electric (red) field strength along a time/space axis (black).

at the alignment point must be such that there is some relation between the energy stored in the magnetic potential and in the electric potential (probably equality).

2.2 Quantising electric potential into apparent charge

This paper posits a new force created by displacing two regions of space off the current time plain. Heisenberg would have guessed that this force would be a function of the time displacement and the amount of energy involved. In order to create a displacement Newton would have argued you need to push backwards as well as forwards so the force required to create a displacement requires two ends. We call this new kind of force a *time like force*.

The force required to hold two rotating dipoles together (the *time like force* associated with their space and time displacement) must equal the centrifugal force associated with the rotating motion of the regions. It is thought that there are a very small number of stable solutions and this is the source of the quantisation of apparent charge.

The dipoles in the *Sinclair Pair* in a Maxwell Spin Cup have the property that the wave function appears to be a duplicate of itself after $1/2$ a rotation but they are not a direct duplicate until 1 full rotation, this may lead an observer to miss-read the angular momentum. I am just going to wave my arms in the air here and wait for a someone else to do the maths to prove this is the origin of spin $1/2$ ness.

2.2.1 Neutrinos

In short dropping magnetic field potentials from a Maxwell Spin Cup leaves behind two regions of space: one pushed forwards in time, the other pushed

Figure 4: Illustrative effect of local time like drag on one side of a photon. Note the blue field line becoming non singular valued as it passes a location with large GR gradient.

backwards in time rotating round each other. This entity is the simplest *Sinclair Pair* and it has intrinsic angular momentum of $\pm 1/2$ spin. This proposed entity seems to correspond to a neutrino.

3 Quarks

Quarks can be created in the fallout from high energy electron-positron collisions. Quarks have innate electrical potential and exist in tightly bound clusters of two or three quarks. The most surprising and interesting property of quarks is that the force between a pair of quarks rises with the distance they are apart (rather than falling off as $\frac{1}{r^2}$ like in some field potential process). Further evidence that charge is not fundamentally quantised is obvious in the non unity electrical potential of quarks. The ingredients for making quarks are then limited to space, time, Maxwell's equations and energy. There seems to be a crushing inevitability that given gluon tubes always form rings with quarks strung round them that the gluon tube is a conduit that contains a discontinuity in space time and the quarks are locks to prevent the rift from sliding back into alignment. Again there is very likely nothing innately quantised about space time but the gubbins

to maintain the rift only has certain stable configurations. The idea of space time tears has been around for a while [9] but the practitioners failed to stumble upon a viable tearing process.

If I had to guess where to look for a tearing process to generate gluon rings I would look for a fast rotating region of space and then pass a high space/time gradient center through it, the rift occurs when some portion of the rotating region thinks it has exceeded the speed of light.

4 Future Work

It remains to crunch the numbers to make sure *Maxwell Spin Cups* can stably exist and have a basin of attraction where if you nearly make one it will bleed off electrical potential and insure magnetic potential rotation matches the time like force that holds them together. The author wondered is there could exist a second type of *Maxwell Spin Cup* in which the *Sinclair Pair* contained an electric potential rather than the familiar magnetic one but as magnetic monopoles do not exist he did not spend a lot of time wondering about it.

The author wondered if the electric field should be considered as a dimension in its own right but is unsure how to do this in a mathematically reasonable way as the dimension is complex. Time displacement from the current time plane is also going to have to be studied.

There may be hidden cleverness in the regions of space time that have been pushed forwards and backwards in time, they may in some sense be rotating themselves and the mechanism for their creation may provide a clue to generation of cheap torsion fields.

5 Conclusions

This paper posits a model for a mechanism by which electric potential can be localised and quantised. This shows charge does not exist so there is nothing intrinsically special about its familiar quantisation. The existence of Cooper-pairs is a function of the the differing sense of the magnetic quadruple like polarisations associated with rotating [N-SS-N] and [S-NN-S] Maxwell Spin Cups. A mechanism is proposed for how scattering events create pairs of *Maxwell Spin Cups*. The paper explains the mechanics of spin 1/2 particles and predicts the existence of neutrinos. No additional dimensions are required only Maxwell's equations and General Relativity. The new idea is that you can create a force in space by displacing two regions of space time away from the current time plane. All of the quandaries about point charges are irrelevant, any theory that relies on the intrinsic quantisation of charge is no longer justifiable (because charge does not exist). It short wave functions are fine but there is no innate reason to try and quantise anything.

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The author acknowledges that the train of thought that lead to this paper started with a conversation at the Cambridge beer festival. I wanted a plausible space drive for a smutty scifi novel I was writing and things drifted to the subject of the Hobson GR Reaction Mass less Torsion Drive (the Hobson Custard Drive) and how looking at quarks might provide a cheaper and less custardy alternative. You simply can't get away from the fact that the force between quarks is spring like and the only fundamental thing in physics that behaves like a spring is Heisenberg's uncertainty principle and it involves time $\delta E \delta t = \lambda$.

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